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Project Acronym: FORWARD

Project title: Forward-Models of Cosmic Dawn: connecting 21cm simulations to the real world

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Version and date of the DMP: Version 2, 20/10/2025

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

ABSTRACT

FORWARD will enable a new generation of transformational probes of Cosmic Dawn (CD) to provide meaningful inference on key questions of galaxy formation. The CD contains some of the most sought-after insights into galaxy formation. Though these secrets remain locked away by a host of formidable real-world challenges, upcoming radio telescopes are optimistic. Interferometers such as HERA and future SKA, along with global experiments such as EDGES-3 are honed to observe the faint 21cm emission from neutral Hydrogen, redshifted to 50-150 MHz, in complementary ways. The dominant limitation of current experiments are spectral systematics that couple with overwhelmingly bright foregrounds. As we enter the regime in which the most extreme physical models begin to be ruled out by observations, meaningful inference of key parameters is most susceptible to inaccuracies in accounting for these systematics. Prior efforts to provide parameter constraints from CD have focused on forecasts, and treated systematics crudely and optimistically. FORWARD will synthesise the popular semi-numerical simulation code 21cmFAST and a radically overhauled parameter-inference engine, 21cmMC-2, with a series of new pluggable modules designed to efficiently forward-model the response of realistic interferometers, enabling the most direct comparison of theory to data. By applying this novel machinery jointly to observations from HERA and EDGES-3, we will (i) provide meaningful constraints on the parameters of galaxy formation during CD, (ii) build confidence in the reported detections, and (iii) enable future joint constraints from the SKA & EDGES-3. The framework developed will follow a legacy of code excellence, providing a bedrock for state-of-the-art developments over the coming years.

FORWARD

Version 2

Description

This is a Data Management Plan for the MSCA project "FORWARD".

Funder

European Commission | EC

Grant

Forward-Models of Cosmic Dawn:
connecting 21cm simulations to the
real world
No 101067043

Researchers

Steven Murray (orcid:0000-0003-3059-3823)

Organizations

SCUOLA NORMALE SUPERIORE

Main Info

Title of DMP: [FORWARD](#)

Description: This is a Data Management Plan for the MSCA project "FORWARD".

Researchers: [Steven Murray \(orcid:0000-0003-3059-3823\)](#)

Organizations: [SCUOLA NORMALE SUPERIORE](#)

Contact: [Steven Murray](#)

Funding

Funding organizations: [European Commission](#) | [EC](#)

Grants: [Forward-Models of Cosmic Dawn: connecting 21cm simulations to the real world](#)

Project: [Forward-Models of Cosmic Dawn: connecting 21cm simulations to the real world](#)

License

License: [MIT](#)

Access Rights: [Public](#)

Templates

Descriptions

The DMP outlines four datasets, as summarized in the table below. It's important to note that both the reused and generated by the project datasets are described in accordance with the Annotated Grant Agreement: "The requirements for research data management apply only to data that are generated in the course of the action. Beneficiaries should also consider re-used data when developing their data management plans (DMPs), if they form part of their research and to the extent possible." (AGA, p. 375).

Dataset Name	Dataset Type	Generated/Re-used
Posterior Samples	Models	Generated
Software	Digital	Generated
HERA Raw Data	Digital	Re-used
EDGES Raw Data	Digital	Re-used

Posterior Samples

This Project will generate a number of posterior samples from inferences on real and synthetic data. These posterior samples will be published.

Template: [Horizon Europe](#)

Type: [Dataset](#)

1 Brief description

This dataset consists of digitally-store simulation models, generated within the project.

Each posterior sample will be its own HDF5 file. The HDF5 file format is self-describing, in that it contains its own metadata. The HDF5 format is widely-used in astronomy, and has software available in many languages (including C and Python) to read from and write to the format. The collection of all files will be paired with a lightweight database (SQLite) to enable easy selection of samples from a particular parameter range, for example.

The size of each file will be dominated by the 2D power spectra, which consist of about 10000 values. Budgeting for 100k posterior samples, the total size will be of order 10 GB per posterior distribution.

These posterior samples will represent the current best estimates at our understanding of astrophysical processes during Cosmic Dawn, accounting for instrumental and systematic uncertainties.

The data will be produced via simulations from the 21cmFAST simulator, with instrumental effects from the matvis and hera_sim codes. The provenance of each file will be written into the metadata of the file itself (including software versions, simulation date/time, parameters etc.).

The posterior samples of the astrophysical parameters, which form part of this Dataset, directly encode our best knowledge of the astrophysical processes in the first billion years of Cosmic history. This knowledge is useful to the 21cm cosmology community, and can be taken and used in further predictive scenarios. Furthermore, the derived quantities such as global signal estimates and 2D power spectra can be used to train emulators and other statistical algorithms to be applied in future analyses.

2 Links to Existing Datasets

2.1 Publications

This dataset does not support any existing publication.

2.2 Datasets

This dataset does not support or use any existing published dataset.

2.3 Software

This dataset uses and is produced by the following software repositories:

- <https://github.com/21cmfast/21cmfast>;
- <https://github.com/21cmfast/21cmMC>;
- https://github.com/hera-team/pspec_likelihood

3 Data and Metadata Formats

3.1 Making Data Findable, Including Provisions For Metadata

The published datasets will be hosted on Zenodo, and include both DOIs and ORCIDs for the authors. Each sub-dataset will be published on Zenodo, which uses a modified metadata scheme based on the DataCite Metadata Schema.

Zenodo metadata includes both Descriptive and Administrative components (e.g. keywords/subjects for Descriptive, and authors, version etc. for Administrative).

Furthermore, the data themselves include metadata in their self-documenting formats (HDF5) that describe the structural composition of the data.

Zenodo employs standardised vocabularies for some of its metadata fields (e.g. RelatedIdentifiers), for which details can be found at: https://openaire-guidelines-for-literature-repository-managers.readthedocs.io/en/latest/field_relatedidentifier.html.

Zenodo provides searchable and harvestable metadata, with keywords.

3.2 Repository

The data will be deposited in Zenodo: <https://zenodo.org>. Zenodo is a large general-purpose scientific data repository. This repository is a trusted source, which (i) Follows repository standards, (ii) Details terms of use, (iii) Has an open access content policy, (iv) Supports retention, (v) Supports withdrawal, (vi) Provides Open Access content (free at the point of use), (vii) Assigns PIDs, (viii) Follows metadata standards, (ix) Supports mid- and long-term preservation, (x) Supports authentication and authorization of users, and (xi) Has data security mechanisms in place, (xii) Assigns persistent identifiers, (xiii) Resolves identifiers to a digital object, and (xiv) Supports versioning.

3.3 Data

The title of this dataset is “HERA/EDGES posterior distributions”. It will be shared via Zenodo.

The dataset will be accessible simply by downloading from Zenodo (e.g. through a web- browser). However, to read the data in a structured way (for example, to make plots from it) will require the HDF5 library. The simplest way to use this library for astronomers will be through the Python library h5py. If a user has Python installed (download from <https://python.org>) then h5py can be installed from a command-line with the command `pip install h5py``.

The HDF5 files will be self-annotated to describe their contents (data array shapes, physical units, etc.).

No access committee supports the dataset.

Zenodo will only track anonymized views/downloads of the resource since it will be available as open-access. Zenodo maintains data for *at least* 20 years, see <https://about.zenodo.org/policies/>

3.4 Metadata

The metadata will be provided under the Creative Commons Zero (CC0) license. This metadata provides information about how to access the described dataset.

3.5 Making Data and Other Outputs Interoperable

The metadata uses a controlled vocabulary, since Zenodo uses controlled vocabularies for many of its metadata fields. We will apply the DataCite Metadata (standard) scheme to the metadata.

The data is store in HDF5 files. HDF5 files are very commonly used in astronomy. Metadata is stored in a consistent way in the files. The files can be opened in most common

programming languages. The dataset does not provide qualified references with other outputs.

3.6 Increasing Reuse of Data and Other Outputs

The data will be published on Zenodo in HDF5 format, with an included Readme file containing variable definitions, and HDF5 internally stores units of measurement in its metadata.

Data provenance will be handled by Zenodo, which keeps records of data versions. Versions of software used to produce the data (at any given version of the data) will be recorded directly into the data files as HDF5 attributes. Data integrity and conformance to the format specification will be assured by its direct use in research publications.

4 Allocation of Resources

The cost of making this dataset FAIR will be zero, since hosting on Zenodo is free for datasets smaller than 50 GB. The PI, Steven Murray, will be responsible for dataset creation and maintenance.

5 Data Security

The data will be open-access, and Zenodo does not require authentication in order to read/download the data. However, data writing/management is restricted to authenticated users (password protected).

The data will be preserved for at least 20 years according to Zenodo's long-term storage plan.

6 Ethical Aspects

There are no ethical or legal issues regarding sharing this dataset, nor does it contain sensitive information.

7 Other

No other procedures for data management are being used.

Software Packages

1 Brief description

A significant aspect of the FORWARD project is the development of software that contributes to a forward-modelling pipeline for 21 cm cosmology inference. These packages will be designed to model the raw data mentioned in the Datasets "HERA Raw Data" and "EDGES Raw Data" above. The software is *modular* and will therefore appear as a number of separate software packages, which in many ways will work together to form the overall pipeline.

Some of these software packages already exist and will be *further* developed within FORWARD (eg. a new major version), and a number of new components/packages will be developed from scratch. In all cases, the guidelines set forth in this Dataset will be followed. The list of software packages that are expected to be significantly developed in

this project are:

- 21cmFAST (v4): <https://github.com/21cmFAST/21cmFAST> -- simulator of the 21cm signal as 4D lightcones
- 21cmMC (pre-existing, but major v1 planned in this project): <https://github.com/21cmFAST/21cmMC> -- Bayesian sampler that uses 21cmFAST as its model
- 21cmSense (v2): <https://github.com/rasg-affiliates/21cmSense> -- sensitivity calculator for 21cm interferometers
- cosmotile (new): <https://github.com/steven-murray/cosmotile> -- tool for creation of lightcones from 3D coeval simulations.
- pygsdata (new): <https://github.com/edges-collab/pygsdata> -- data-interface for global 21cm experiments
- pspec-likelihood (new): https://github.com/hera-team/pspec_likelihood -- abstracted likelihood interface for observed 21cm power spectra
- edges-estimate (new): <https://github.com/edges-collab/edges-estimate> -- modular likelihoods for EDGES data, including systematic effects
- matvis (new): <https://github.com/hera-team/matvis> -- fast, GPU-accelerated wide-field radio interferometer simulator
- edges-beam-emulator (new) -- emulation of EDGES beams given input physical parameters
edges-sim (new) -- high-realism simulator of EDGES data, with modular systematic effects.

The packages described here are written in a combination of C and Python, but also have documentation written in ReStructured Text (RST) format, as well as demonstration examples written as Jupyter Notebooks. These are standard choices within astrophysics software, and are generally highly interoperable.

The number of packages described here is about 10 (variations exist in practice due to changing modelling assumptions). Each repository is of order a few MB.

The packages in this Dataset are being generated/re-used to obtain information, via:

- Analysis of 21cm single-antenna data (e.g. pygsdata, 21cmSense)
- Simulation of 21 cm cosmological signals (e.g. 21cmFAST, cosmotile)

- Bayesian forward-modelling of instrumental effects and cosmology (e.g. 21cmMC, edges-sim, edges-beam-emulator)

The packages here described originated in large part directly from the Researcher. Some of the packages (e.g. 21cmFAST, 21cmMC, 21cmSense) were originally created by other researchers, and the Researcher has made significant contributions that led them to their current state. In all cases, the packages were not *solely* produced by the Researcher in isolation. They either have explicit involvement from the research community (generally the 21cm cosmology community) via direct code contributions (via Github Pull Requests), or at the very least have been designed based on interactions and suggestions from the 21cm cosmology community.

These packages have been and will be developed with the community in mind. While some of them are very specific in their scope, others are quite general purpose. All of them will be developed in a way that encourages their use outside of the original intended application. For instance, pygsdata was created in the context of handling EDGES data, but with a view to it being more generally applicable to the data from any drift-scan-style global experiment (there are several of these around the globe). Due to this generalization, explicit discussions are underway between the Researcher and members of these other experiments to optimize the scope and implementation of pygsdata to enable it to be used as their data-handling library. In the end, this will facilitate seamless data-sharing between experiments.

2 Links to Existing Datasets

2.1 Publications

One of the packages included in this Dataset supports an existing scientific publication:

- matvis: A matrix-based visibility simulator for fast forward modelling of many-element 21 cm arrays deposited in arXiv.org e-Print Archive (<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2312.09763>).

This publication provides information about where to find the software package.

2.2 Datasets

This Dataset does not use or support other existing published datasets.

3 Data and Metadata Formats

3.1 Making Data Findable, Including Provisions For Metadata

Each software package will be published in at least three ways, according to typical standards for astronomy code:

- As a Github Release
- As a PyPI package
- As a Zenodo dataset (linked to the Github release). This automatically assigns a DOI for the package, and links to ORCID IDs for the authors.

Some of the codes may also be published with a linked journal article which will reference the same Zenodo-generated DOI and ORCID IDs.

We use standard metadata for Python projects: the `pyproject.toml` file, which is readable both by the PyPI package index and the conda package database, which are the package repositories automatically used to install software by most astronomers.

Furthermore, the packages will be published on Zenodo, which applies a modified version of the DataCite Metadata Schema. We will ensure that the metadata is filled out to the fullest extent possible, rather than simply relying on the Github Release integration in Zenodo, which fills out only a minimal subset.

The metadata defines the package name, authors, description, version and other important characteristics of the software. The metadata use standard vocabularies:

- Links to related publications from the software: https://openaire-guidelines-for-literature-repository-managers.readthedocs.io/en/latest/field_relatedidentifier.html
- A list of descriptive tags concerning Python repositories (development stage, intended audience, etc): <https://pypi.org/classifiers/>

Metadata is searchable on <https://pypi.org> and also <https://zenodo.org>, as well as OpenAIRE explore (since it harvests Zenodo metadata). All software packages maintain a list of keywords in their `pyproject.toml` files that help them to be identified in the large PyPI database, in addition to their "classifiers" as described above. Furthermore, keywords will be added to the associated Zenodo datasets that draw on a controlled vocabulary.

The metadata are also harvestable via PyPI. The PyPI package index maintains an API from which metadata from a package can be downloaded in JSON format.

3.2 Repository

The dataset (packages) will be deposited on the following repositories:

- Github (<https://github.com>): the most used open-source software repository.
- PyPI (<https://pypi.org>): the Python Packaging Index, which provides metadata and downloadable/installable python packages to the community.
- Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org>): a popular general purpose scientific dataset repo.

These repositories are trusted sources that: (i) Follow repository standards, (ii) detail terms of use, (iii) have an open access content policy, (iv) support retention, (v) support withdrawal, (vi) support back up, (vii) provide open-access content (free at the point of use), (viii) Assign PIDs, (ix) Follow metadata standards, (x) Use non-proprietary formats, (xi) support mid- and long-term preservation, (xi) Support authentication and authorization of users, (xii) have data security mechanisms in place, (xiii) support versioning.

3.3 Data

Each software package is open-source and publicly available on Github (with links provided on Zenodo and PyPI). The title for each package is consistent across repositories.

The software packages are generally written in Python. The source code can be read and edited directly on Github with any modern internet browser, so long as a user has a Github account. However, generally the workflow for contributing to the code is to use the `git` software (available on MacOS, Linux and Windows) to clone a copy of the repo locally, and use any text editor (including basic editors such as Notepad, to more customized solutions such as VS Code) to make edits to the code, submitting these edits with the `git` tool.

To *use* the codes (rather than editing the code) simply requires a Python installation (generally Python 3.8+, though this requirement is listed explicitly in the packages' metadata), which is available on all major operating systems, and a python package manager (eg. `pip` or `conda`) which are also available on any operating system.

The codes were primarily developed with the following tools: git, Github, VSCode and pip.

conda can be downloaded from <https://anaconda.org/> and has the ability to install Python itself.

Python can be independently downloaded and installed from <https://python.org>.

Pip is automatically installed with Python using either of these methods. VS Code can be installed from <https://code.visualstudio.com/>.

All software packages are open-source and maintained on Github, PyPI and Zenodo. These repositories will retain the data irrespective of the start/end of this Project. The packages will be available for as long as the host repositories exist (20+ years guaranteed in the case of Zenodo).

3.4 Metadata

The metadata will be provided under a Creative Commons Zero (CC0) license. The metadata provides links to the Github repository which provides access to the data. In the unforeseen circumstance that the packages are removed from Github and/or Zenodo, the metadata on Zenodo will be kept.

3.5 Making Data and Other Outputs Interoperable

The metadata does not use a controlled vocabulary, nor use a standard schema. We do not provide a mapping to more commonly used ontologies. No qualified references to other outputs are included.

The packages are/will be written in Python, the primary language used by astrophysics researchers. They run on MacOS and Linux, which are the primary operating systems used in astrophysics research. They provide a clean and openly documented API so that it can be easily adopted.

3.6 Increasing Reuse of Data and Other Outputs

The dataset will be made available under the MIT License. The repositories include README files that detail installation methods and usage, as well as web-hosted documentation explaining usage. The data will be provided in the public domain, and remain available after the project finishes. Github uses git as a versioning system, so all commits are tracked. Zenodo also keeps track of the Release versions. All packages will be well-tested, using the pytest unit-testing software. This will be enforced through the use of standard Continuous Integration services, such as Github Actions, which run the tests (and other quality checks) automatically on every commit to the repositories.

4 Allocation of Resources

It will not cost anything to make the dataset FAIR, since Github, PyPI and Zenodo are free for open-source repositories. The PI, Steven Murray, will be responsible for managing the packages, with support from collaborators.

5 Data Security

While the code is open-source and available to read without any authentication, it can be contributed to only by authenticated Github users (Github uses passwords as well as 2FA). Such users must submit Pull Requests that are reviewed by code Admins (i.e. the PI).

Github has a range of strategies for preserving the repositories it hosts, both in the near- and long-term future. See <https://archiveprogram.github.com/approach/>

Zenodo also has a long-term retention policy of over 20 years.

6 Ethical Aspects

There are no ethical or legal issues that impact the sharing of the dataset, nor does it contain sensitive or personal information.

7 Other

No other procedures for data management are being used.

HERA Raw Data

1 Brief description

HERA is a radio interferometer in South Africa, operated by a medium-sized collaboration based in the US. It measures thousands of correlated sky signals on a cadence of ~ 10 sec, and has been operating for several years. This dataset describes the raw observed data, and does *not* cover processed datasets that arise from analysing the raw HERA data.

This dataset describes digitally-stored Research data, which this project is *re-using* rather than generating. The data is produced by the HERA team, of which the PI is a part. However the data is not actively produced as a part of this Project, rather it is being studied/analysed. The data is observational, consisting of interferometric visibilities between 50-250 MHz.

HERA data is primarily stored in the `uvh5` format, which is a specific standard leveraging the fast and well-used HDF5 file format underneath. The `uvh5` format is defined within the `pyuvdata` Python software, which is [publicly available](#). That software also provides methods for reading and writing to/from `uvh5` files. The `uvh5` format is a general-purpose format for radio interferometric data, and is not specific to HERA data.

Each day of observation is between 500-2000 GB (increasing over time due to larger number of deployed antennas). A full 'season' contains ~ 120 days of observation, and is therefore 50-200 TB. At the conclusion of this Project, 8 seasons of data will have been collected, resulting in ~ 1 PB of data.

This raw data forms the basis of scientific investigations of the conditions of the early universe. It will be processed and analysed within this project. HERA data is observed by the instrument in South Africa, and copied to a data store hosted by the NRAO (National Radio Astronomy Observatory) in the US as a continuous process. This data is immediately useful for researchers in the HERA team, who process and analyse it, and publish results based on it. At that stage it becomes useful to the wider research community.

2 Links to Existing Datasets

2.1 Publications

The described output supports many publications, but none linked to this project (yet).

2.2 Software

This dataset used the following software in order to produce and store it:

- <https://github.com/hera-team>
- <https://github.com/RadioAstronomySoftwareGroup/pyuvdata>

3 Data and Metadata Formats

3.1 Making Data Findable, Including Provisions For Metadata

HERA Data is hosted on large NRAO storage drives, and is not public. While datafiles within the dataset contain metadata, no metadata that describes the dataset as a whole exists.

3.2 Repository

The data is hosted by NRAO and is not public. This is primarily due to its size and complexity.

3.3 Data

The title of this dataset is “HERA Raw Data”. It is not publicly shared, though may be in a future date. The data does not belong to the PI, but the HERA team. The principal reasons for limited access are:

- To enable researchers in the team to gain the benefit of the data before making it public.
- To guard against inappropriate interpretations of the data, which is quite complex and requires significant knowledge of the system to interpret correctly.
- Due to its size (~1PB) it is difficult to share.

The raw data is stored on a dedicated long-term-storage drive hosted by the National Radio Astronomy Observatory (NRAO) in the USA. Read-only access to the data requires a user account on the NRAO system and an SSH connection. In order to read the data in a meaningful way, the open-source Python package `pyuvdata` is required. Tools for understanding, calibrating and plotting the data are maintained by the HERA team in open-source repositories at <https://github.com/hera-team>.

SSH is typically installed by default on MacOS and Linux operating systems. On Windows it can be used from within a WSL2 environment, or via third-party implementations.

Python can be downloaded from <https://python.org>.

pyuvdata can be installed (with its dependencies) once python is installed by typing the command ``pip install pyuvdata``.

All HERA software can be installed in a similar manner.

The HERA board meets to discuss requests for data access (the PI is not on the board). The Researcher has an NRAO account and therefore has access to the data. There is no specific access agreement in place between the Researcher and the HERA Collaboration/Board, however it is understood that publications based on the data should be subjected to the Publication Policy within the HERA Collaboration Agreement (this agreement is not publicly available). Briefly, publications that arise from using HERA data must undergo a specific timeline: first the draft must be disseminated to the collaboration, after which the results are presented to the collaboration via telecon, comments are received and responded to, and then the paper can be submitted. HERA Data cannot be shared directly without explicit approval from the Board.

Since the Researcher's access to the HERA data is not tied to this project, but rather tied to being a part of the HERA collaboration, access will remain the same after the project ends. Data access has no specific end.

3.4 Metadata

Comprehensive metadata will not be publicly available until the data itself is publicly available. This is not in the power of the PI to change. If/when it becomes available, the metadata will be provided under a Creative Commons Zero (CC0) license. The metadata will provide information about how to access the dataset.

3.5 Making Data and Other Outputs Interoperable

The metadata does not use a controlled vocabulary, nor apply a standard scheme, nor map to more commonly used ontologies or provide qualified references to other outputs. However, The ``.uvh5`` format used for HERA data uses a well-defined and community-established standard for both data storage and metadata definition, documented publicly at <https://pyuvdata.readthedocs.org>. The use of the ``.uvh5`` data format is community-endorsed and enables other teams to load/analyse HERA data (if access is provided).

3.6 Increasing Reuse of Data and Other Outputs

The data currently has no license as it is not publicly available. However, if/when it does become publicly available, it will be reusable because the analysis pipelines used to reduce the data are stored and already publicly available.

The raw data described here essentially has no lineage -- it is kept raw from the instrument. However, processed data arising from the raw data contains internal history of its

transformation. All data are written in specified formats, and the code used to read them performs checks on these formats, ensuring that the data conform to format specifications.

4 Allocation of Resources

While there is a significant cost for data management, this is not covered by this Project, but rather the HERA team. The PI of the HERA project, Dr. Aaron Parsons (orcid:0000-0002-5400-8097) is responsible for managing the dataset.

5 Data Security

Currently, data is accessible only via the servers at NRAO, which can only be accessed with a valid account (and secured by password). The NRAO data service has long-term storage policies, and the HERA team is considering long-term cloud-storage for the raw data. Inevitably, the full raw data cannot be kept ad infinitum, and so reduced/processed datasets will be considered for longer-term storage.

6 Ethical Aspects

There are no ethical or legal issues regarding sharing this dataset, nor does it contain sensitive information.

7 Other

No other procedures for data management are being used.

EDGES Raw Data

1 Brief description

EDGES is a single-antenna radio telescope in Western Australia. It observes sky-averaged spectra on a cadence of ~ 40 sec, and has been operating for several years. This dataset describes both the raw observed data from the sky, and the calibration data taken in the lab at ASU which the EDGES team produces. This dataset does *not* cover processed datasets that arise from analysing the raw EDGES data.

This is digitally-stored Research Data, produced by the EDGES team, of which the Researcher is a part. It is being reused for this project.

The data described here is both observational and experimental, though the more important (and larger) part of the data is observational. It consists of spectra of the sky between 50-250 MHz, as well as calibration spectra taken in the lab.

EDGES observational data is written in a few formats:

- Spectra: these are written as binary files, in a custom format designed by the EDGES team, called ".acq" files. This format can be read and written by the python code

`read_acq`, which is publicly available on Github at https://github.com/edges-collab/read_acq.

- Reflection coefficient measurements: these are ASCII files with a specific format (".s1p") and can be read using the publicly available `edges-io` code at <https://github.com/edges-collab/edges-io>.
- Receiver Temperature Logs: these are simple CSV files, readable by the publicly available `edges-io` code
- Weather logs: these are simply CSV files, readable by the publicly available `edges-io` code

Current size of EDGES-2 observational data (all types) is 3TB. Size of EDGES-3 Calibration data is 0.5 TB. Size of EDGES-3 data is 0.5TB. Expectation is for 1TB more in the next two years. This raw data forms the basis of scientific investigations of the conditions of the early universe. It will be processed and analysed within this project. EDGES data is observed by the instrument in Western Australia, and copied to a server at ASU (Arizona State University) every night. EDGES calibration data is observed in the lab at ASU on an irregular cadence, and copied to the same server at ASU. This data is immediately useful for researchers in the EDGES team, who process and analyse it, and publish results based on it. At that stage it becomes useful to the wider research community.

2 Links to Existing Datasets

2.1 Publications

The described output supports many publications, but none linked to this project (yet). A data availability statement is available here: Yes

<https://www.nature.com/articles/nature25792#Sec2>

2.2 Software

This dataset used the following software in order to produce and store it:

- <https://github.com/edges-collab>

3 Data and Metadata Formats

3.1 Making Data Findable, Including Provisions For Metadata

The raw EDGES data has not been published directly, nor is it hosted on any repository (e.g. Zenodo). It is hosted internally on storage hard-drives at Arizona State University. The metadata for the dataset is not provided, and the Researcher does not control the publication or hosting of this dataset.

3.2 Repository

The data is hosted by ASU and is not public. This is partly due to its size and complexity.

The storage at ASU is on a data cluster maintained by the low-frequency cosmology group. It is regularly serviced and upgraded, and has redundancy (RAID) applied for data security.

3.3 Data

The title of this dataset is “EDGS Raw Data”. It is not publicly shared, though may be in a future date. The data does not belong to the PI, but the EDGES team. The principal reasons for limited access are:

- To enable researchers in the team to gain the benefit of the data before making it public.
- To guard against inappropriate interpretations of the data, which is quite complex and requires significant knowledge of the system to interpret correctly.
- Due to its size (>3 TB) it is difficult to share.

The EDGES team meets to discuss requests for data access. The Researcher has access to the EDGES Raw Data by having a user account on the ASU storage cluster (all such users have read-access to the data, even if they are not formally a part of the team). No conditions are set on data use, other than that the data should not be shared outside the team without discussion with the team first. Reading/processing/writing of the data is assisted by custom software written by the team which is publicly available (<https://github.com/edges-collab>)

Access to the data is limited to those with a user account on the cluster at ASU, which can be requested by contacting the administrators (or via an EDGES team member). In special circumstances, small subsets of the data may be shared with researchers outside the EDGES team via other means (e.g. dropbox, Google Drive) upon request. Data access has no specific end. The Researcher has unlimited access to the data by virtue of being a team member, and no specific access agreement is in place.

3.4 Metadata

Comprehensive metadata will not be publicly available until the data itself is publicly available. This is not in the power of the PI to change. If/when it becomes available, the metadata will be provided under a Creative Commons Zero (CC0) license. The metadata will provide information about how to access the dataset.

3.5 Making Data and Other Outputs Interoperable

The metadata does not use a controlled vocabulary, nor apply a standard scheme, nor map to more commonly used ontologies or provide qualified references to other outputs. Most of the data formats that EDGES uses are widely used (eg. CSV), and these files have

appropriate metadata inside them (though no overarching metadata exists for the entire dataset). The spectra are in a custom format, but EDGES provides a publicly-available code to read/write this data. This code is written in Python, which is the most widely used language in astronomy. While the data itself is not highly interoperable, the EDGES team is developing code that is able to read/write the data formats, and eases cross-compatibility with similar spectral data from other experiments. This code exists here:

<https://github.com/edges-collab/pygsdata>.

3.6 Increasing Reuse of Data and Other Outputs

The data currently has no license as it is not publicly available. However, if/when it does become publicly available, it will use a Creative Commons Attribution-Non Commercial 4.0 license.

The raw data described here essentially has no lineage -- it is kept raw from the instrument. However, processed data arising from the raw data contains internal history of its transformation. All data are written in specified formats, and the code used to read them performs checks on these formats, ensuring that the data conform to format specifications.

4 Allocation of Resources

While there is a significant cost for data management, this is not covered by this Project, but rather the EDGES team. The PI of the EDGES project, Dr. Judd Bowman (orcid: 0000-0002-8475-2036) is responsible for managing the dataset.

5 Data Security

Currently, data is accessible only via the servers at ASU, which can only be accessed with a valid account (and secured by password). The server on which the data is currently hosted has RAID enabled so that it has redundancy in case of hard drive failure.

6 Ethical Aspects

There are no ethical or legal issues regarding sharing this dataset, nor does it contain sensitive information.

7 Other

No other procedures for data management are being used.